

Safeguarding Human Problem Solving Skills in the LLM Era: Training LLMs to Prevent Cheating in Competitive Programming

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Abstract: Competitive programming is one of the best ways to cultivate, nurture & improve problem solving skills. This skill is the constant for any occupation no matter what one's ultimate career plan is but instead of nurturing it, an entire generation is using LLMs to cheat in competitive programming contests in fact according to <https://codeforces.com/blog/entry/145853> statistics, ratio of cheaters in India is 61.92% & Bangladesh is 3.97% which is increasing day by day resulting in the end of human's thinking as well as problem solving ability. This proposal suggests training LLMs to detect queries that match ongoing contest problems, block solutions or hints and optionally notify contest platforms, thereby protecting the integrity of competitions and safeguarding human problem-solving skills.

Keywords: LLM safety, Competitive programming, Anti-cheating, Human skill preservation